

STUDIES IN AZO DYES. PART I

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Azo dyes, derived from thioindoxyl, 5-phenylthioindoxyl and 4:5-benzothioindoxyl, have been synthesised with a view to studying the relation between colour and chemical constitution.

Friedländer (*Monatsh.*, 1907, 30, 347) first showed that benzenediazonium chloride or its *p*-nitro derivative coupled with 3-hydroxythionaphthene to yield orange-red dyes. A search in the literature reveals that no systematic study of this class of azo dyes has yet been made, excepting that by the Russian workers (Rodionov *et al.*, *J. Appl. Chem.*, U.S.S.R., 1948, 21, 962; *Chem. Abs.*, 1949, 43, 6204) who coupled diazotised benzidine, *p*-nitroaniline and *p*-aminoacetanilide with 3-hydroxythionaphthene and obtained the corresponding azo dyes. They did not, however, study the effect of constitution on the colour of these dyes.

Azo dyes derived from thioindoxyl, 5-phenylthioindoxyl and 4:5-benzothioindoxyl have been synthesised by coupling diazotised amines, e.g., *p*-nitroaniline, *p*-bromoaniline, β -naphthylamine, *p*-toluidine, aniline, sulphanilic acid, anthranilic acid, with these thioindoxyls. As the thioindoxyls undergo quick oxidation, particularly in alkaline medium, the cold alkaline solution after filtration was immediately coupled with the diazotised amine solutions, cooled in ice, when the azo dyes were precipitated. The dyes are soluble in alcohol, acetic acid, xylene and other organic solvents. These produce characteristic colour with concentrated sulphuric acid. The absorption maxima have been determined in xylene solution excepting those derived from amino-sulphonic acids, which are insoluble in xylene. The structure of these dyes is represented by the following general formula :

[where $R_2 = \text{Ph}$; $R_1 = R_2 = \text{benzo}$; $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{phenyl}$, substituted phenyl, naphthyl as the case may be]

Martinet (*Rev. Gen. Mat. Col.*, 1921, 25, 17) has shown that substitution in 5-position in thioindoxyl renders the thioindigoid dyes deeper in colour. This appears to be true also in this series of azo dyes as 5-phenylthioindoxyl affords azo dyes of deeper colour than those obtained from unsubstituted thioindoxyl. Further, it is known that in the case of indigoid dyes, if additional benzene ring is fused in 4:5-position, the colour of the dyes is not enhanced, rather becomes

lighter than the parent dyes. This observation seems to be in conformity with the azo dyes derived from 4:5-benzothioindoxyl, where the colour does not become deeper. Of course, the generalisation requires far more systematic study.

EXPERIMENTAL

The following general method was followed for the preparation of the thioindoxyl dyes.

A solution of the amine (1.1 M) in HCl (dil., 2M) was diluted and cooled in an ice-bath to 0°.5° and stirred mechanically. A strong solution of sodium nitrite (1 M) was added dropwise until the solution tested weak blue with starch-iodide paper. The filtered and cooled diazo solution was then added quickly to the cold filtered solution of thioindoxyl, 4:5-benzothioindoxyl and 5-phenylthioindoxyl in sufficient aqueous NaOH solution (2N) so that the solution remained alkaline after the addition; the mixture was stirred mechanically for sometime. The precipitated azo dyes were filtered after half an hour, washed thoroughly with water, macerated with HCl (dil.), filtered and washed free of acid. Crystallisation from either dilute alcohol or acetic acid yielded shining crystals of the azo dyes. In the case of sulphanic and anthranilic acids, the dyes were precipitated on acidifying the alkaline solution. The various properties of the compounds, as studied, are recorded in the following tables.

TABLE I

3-Hydroxythionaphthene azo dyes.

Compound.	M.P.	Colour of crystals.	Colour in H ₂ SO ₄ .	λ_{max} .	Formula.	% Nitrogen. Found. Calc.
*T-2-(<i>p</i> -nitro)azobenzene	>290°	Brownish red	Violet	500m μ	C ₁₄ H ₉ O ₃ N ₃ S	14.00 14.04
T-2-(<i>p</i> -bromo)azobenzene	164°	Red	Deep red	495	C ₁₄ H ₉ ON ₂ BrS	8.21 8.40
T-2-azobenzene- <i>p</i> -sulphonic acid	>290°	Orange	Blood-red	(Insoluble in xylene)	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	8.41 8.38
T-2-azobenzene- <i>o</i> -carboxylic acid	228°(d)	Brown	Brown	425	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₂ S	9.32 9.40
T-2- β -azonaphthalene	224°	Red needles	Violet	490	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ ON ₂ S	9.18 9.21
T-2- α -azonaphthalene-4-sulphonic acid	159°(d)	Violet	Violet	(Insoluble in xylene)	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	7.19 7.30

* T denotes 3-hydroxythionaphthene.

TABLE II

3-Hydroxy-4:5-benzothionaphthene-azo dyes.

Compound.	M.P.	Colour of crystals.	Colour in H ₂ SO ₄ .	λ_{max} .	Formula.	% Nitrogen. Found. Calc.
*B-2-(<i>p</i> -nitro)azobenzene	253-56°(d)	Deep red	Purple	510m μ	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃ S	12.02 12.03
B-2-(<i>p</i> -bromo)azobenzene	131-32°	Red	Purple	No maxima	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ ON ₂ Br	7.29 7.31
B-2-azobenzene	105°(d) (sintering at 92°)	Red	Purple	500	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ ON ₂ S	9.15 9.20
B-2- β -azonaphthalene	145-50°	Brown	Violet	525	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	7.85 7.50
B-2-(<i>p</i> -methyl)azobenzene	114-20°	Red	Purple	No maxima	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	8.79 8.80

*B denotes 3-hydroxy-4:5-benzo-thionaphthene.

TABLE III

5-Phenyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene-azo dyes.

Compound.	M.P.	Colour of crystals.	Colour in H ₂ SO ₄ .	$\lambda_{\max}$.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Calc.
*P-1-azobenzene	158°	Chocolate-red	Deep red	450m μ	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ ON ₂ S	8.33	8.50
P-2-(<i>p</i> -nitro)azobenzene	181°	Orange-red	Red	500	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ S	11.12	11.20
P-2-azobenzene- <i>p</i> -sulphonic acid	>290°	Scarlet red	Red	(Insoluble in xylene)	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂ S ₂	6.75	6.63
P-2-azobenzene- <i>o</i> -carboxylic acid	269°	Orange-red	Pink	445	C ₂₁ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂ S	7.36	7.48
P-2- β -azonaphthalene	195°	Deep chocolate	Violet	500	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ ON ₂ S	7.28	7.37

*P denotes 5-phenyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene.

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